

PRACTICES AND RESOURCES FOR DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION AND CREATIVITY

Sarviniso Sanakulova

PhD student of Scientific Research Institute of Pedagogical Sciences of Uzbekistan named after
K.Niyazi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11506058>

Abstract. *Creativity is a key skill that can be fostered and enhanced through differentiated instruction, as it allows students to express their original ideas, solve problems, and explore their passions. This article shows some of the best practices and resources for differentiated instruction and creativity.*

Keywords: *creativity, differentiated instruction, flexible grouping, diversity, creative thinking skills, powerful tool.*

Differentiated instruction is a way of teaching that adapts to the diverse learning needs, preferences and interests of students. It involves providing multiple options for content, process and product, as well as varying the level of challenge, support and feedback. Due to individual differences, not every pupil is the same. Based on this knowledge, differentiated instruction is a method of teaching and learning in which pupils have many options for absorbing information and making sense of ideas. The diversified instruction paradigm encourages teachers to be flexible in their approach to teaching and modifying the curriculum and presentation of material to learners, rather than expecting students to modify themselves for the curriculum. Classroom instruction is a combination of whole-class, group, and individual instruction. Differentiated Instruction is a teaching paradigm that holds that educational practices in classrooms should vary and be adaptable to individual and different students. There are some effective ways of differentiated instruction and creativity from the LinkedIn that I found.

Know your students - The first step to differentiate instruction and promote creativity is to know your students well. This means assessing their readiness, interests, and learning profiles, as well as their strengths, challenges, and goals. You can use a variety of tools and strategies to gather this information, such as surveys, interviews, portfolios, observations, pre-tests, and self-assessments. Knowing your students will help you design lessons that are relevant, engaging, and meaningful for them.

Offer choices - One of the most effective ways to differentiate instruction and stimulate creativity is to offer choices to your students. Choices can be given for the content they learn, the process they use, or the product they create. For example, you can let them choose from a menu of topics, activities, or assignments that align with the learning objectives and standards. You can also let them choose the format, mode, or medium of their work, such as writing, drawing, speaking, or digital. Offering choices will empower your students to take ownership of their learning and express their individuality.

Use flexible grouping - Another key strategy to differentiate instruction and foster creativity is to use flexible grouping. This means grouping your students based on different criteria, such as readiness, interest, learning style, or product, and changing the groups frequently and purposefully. Flexible grouping will allow you to tailor your instruction and feedback to the specific needs and goals of each group, as well as to facilitate collaboration, communication, and

peer support. Flexible grouping will also encourage your students to interact with diverse peers, share different perspectives, and learn from each other.

Incorporate creative thinking skills - To differentiate instruction and enhance creativity, you should also incorporate creative thinking skills into your lessons. Creative thinking skills are the cognitive abilities that enable your students to generate, evaluate, and refine ideas. Some examples of creative thinking skills are brainstorming, questioning, divergent thinking, convergent thinking, and metacognition. You can teach and model these skills explicitly, as well as provide opportunities for your students to practice and apply them in various contexts and tasks. Incorporating creative thinking skills will help your students develop their critical and creative thinking abilities and habits of mind.

Use technology - Technology can be a powerful tool to differentiate instruction and support creativity. Technology can help you access and deliver diverse and rich content, as well as provide multiple ways for your students to process and demonstrate their learning. Technology can also enable your students to access personalized and adaptive learning platforms, collaborate and communicate with others online, and create original and innovative products. Some examples of technology tools and resources that can enhance differentiated instruction and creativity are Google Classroom, Flipgrid, Kahoot, Padlet, Canva, and Scratch.

Celebrate diversity and creativity -Finally, to differentiate instruction and nurture creativity, you should celebrate the diversity and creativity of your students. This means recognizing and appreciating the different ways that your students learn, think, and express themselves, as well as providing constructive and positive feedback on their work. You should also create a safe and supportive learning environment that encourages risk-taking, experimentation, and exploration. Celebrating diversity and creativity will boost your students' confidence, motivation, and self-esteem, as well as foster a culture of respect, curiosity, and innovation.

The concept of differentiated instruction describes how to accommodate different learning styles in a classroom environment. Teachers must differentiate their lessons because the students in the classrooms have a variety of needs and come to school with a diversity of experiences. The need to educate all students, including those who are at risk of dropping out of school, have cultural and linguistic differences, are underprivileged, are slow learners, gifted and talented learners, are enrolled in special education, have racial, ethnic, and socioeconomic differences, as well as students with various educational backgrounds and family values, is eminent. As a result, basic school teachers should keep differentiating their lessons to accommodate the varied demands of all these student groups in their classes. The findings indicated that most teachers generally possess a good level of understanding regarding differentiated instructional approaches.

REFERENCES

1. Anderson, K. What does the Literature on Differentiated Instruction Recommend to Teachers who the Needs of all their Students? A research paper submitted to the faculty of the department of physics. 2009
2. Beghetto, R. A. Prospective teachers' beliefs about imaginative thinking in K-12 schooling. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*, 3(2), 134-144. 2007
3. Tuo, X., & Beili, Z. Improving thinking skills in early childhood using effective teaching strategies. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 1359-1789. 2021

4. Арапов А.И. Дифференциация обучения в истории отечественной педагогики и школы. - Новосибирск: НГПУ, 2003, - 243 с.
5. Матвеев, А.В. Уровневая дифференциация как условие самореализации подростков в учебном процессе : дис. ... канд пед. наук: 13.00.01 / А.В. Матвеев. Ярославль, 2001.